

Transition Metal Catalysed Coupling Reactions of Aryl Halides with Acrylic Acid

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The palladium catalysed reactions of organometallic compounds with aryl halides deserve a proper attention¹. The palladium catalysed coupling reactions of aryl halides with olefins are of great importance because of their wide applications in organic synthesis^{2,3}. Recently, the palladium catalysed arylation of methyl acrylate in water, in the presence of potassium or sodium carbonate as the base, has been reported⁴. We reported earlier⁵, the coupling reactions of aryl halides with acrylic acid and acrylonitrile in water, in the presence of palladium as the catalyst. Here we report the palladium catalysed coupling reactions of *o*- and *m*-iodophenol with acrylic acid in water for the synthesis of substituted cinnamic acids (reaction 1) (Table 1).

TABLE I—PALLADIUM-CATALYSED REACTIONS OF CH₂=CHCOOH WITH ArI

Sl. no.	Ar	Reaction temp °C	Reaction time h	Yield %
1.	<i>o</i> -HOC ₆ H ₄	80	2.5	89
2. ^a	<i>o</i> -HOC ₆ H ₄	50	1.5	90
3.	<i>m</i> -HOC ₆ H ₄	80	2.0	93
4. ^a	<i>m</i> -HOC ₆ H ₄	50	1.0	95

^aThe reaction was carried in the presence of CH₃COOK

Results and Discussion

Aryl iodides react with acrylic acid in the presence of palladium acetate as the catalyst and a base (NaHCO₃ or K₂CO₃) in water to give very high yields of substituted cinnamic acids. The reaction proceeds at elevated temperature.

The catalytic cycle of the reaction is proposed in Scheme 1 and is based on the reported mechanism³. Pd⁰ complex is generated *in situ* from the initial palladium complex under the reaction conditions⁶. ArI reacts with Pd⁰

under oxidative addition to give ArPdI complex (a). The latter further adds to the olefin giving an intermediate palladium complex (b) that eliminates hydridopalladium iodide (HPdI) (d) to give an unsaturated compound (c). HPdI (d) then reacts with the base and results in the recovery of Pd⁰ complex.

Scheme 1

From the synthetic viewpoint, it is of interest to study the effect of potassium acetate on the rate of the reaction and temperature conditions. We found that in the presence of CH₃COOK the reaction proceeds at low temperature and with high reaction rate (reactions 2 and 3).

The palladium-catalysed coupling reactions of various olefins with aryl halides give arylated products in high yields, and a few reactions are described here. Synthesis of various β-aryl ketones and aldehydes have been reported⁷ by reacting aryl halides with allylic alcohols. Melpolder and Heck⁸ prepared 3-arylaldehydes and ketones from allylic alcohols and aryl halides, and they also performed reactions of acetals of α-β unsaturated aldehydes with aryl bromides and iodides in the presence of triethylamine to get arylated products⁹. Thus, the palladium-catalysed arylation of unsaturated compounds may be considered to be an efficient and selective method for the synthesis of various olefinic compounds.

Experimental

Aryl halides were prepared by standard procedures. Analytical grade NaHCO₃, K₂CO₃ and CH₃COOK were

used. Acrylic acid and water were used after distillation. Pd(OAc)₂ (Aldrich) was used. The isolated products, *o*-hydroxy- and *m*-hydroxycinnamic acids¹⁰ were identified by elemental analysis, physical and spectral data.

Synthesis of *o*-HOC₆H₄CH=CHCOOH : (a) A mixture of water (2 ml), K₂CO₃ (0.207 g, 1.5 mmol), acrylic acid (0.103 ml, 1.5 mmol), *o*-iodophenol (0.220 g, 1 mmol) and Pd(OAc)₂ (0.00224 g, 0.01 mmol) was stirred at 80° under argon. The reaction mixture was tested by tlc to check for completion of the reaction (after 2.5 h). The reaction mixture was then cooled, filtered and the filtrate was treated with dilute HCl till it became acidic to litmus. The filtrate was extracted with ether (6 × 5 ml). The ether solution was dried over MgSO₄ and then evaporated to give the product (0.146 g, 89%), m.p. 207°¹⁰.

(b) With CH₃COOK as a base : A mixture of water (2 ml), K₂CO₃ (0.173 g, 1.25 mmol), acrylic acid (0.103 ml, 1.5 mmol), *o*-iodophenol (0.220 g, 1 mmol), CH₃COOK (0.098 g, 1 mmol) and Pd(OAc)₂ (0.00224 g, 0.01 mmol) was stirred at 50° under argon. The reaction was complete after 1.5 h (checked by tlc). The mixture was then cooled, filtered and the filtrate was treated with dilute HCl till it became acidic to litmus. The filtrate was extracted with ether (6 × 5 ml). The ether solution was then dried over

MgSO₄ and then evaporated to give the product (0.148 g, 90%), m.p. 207°¹⁰.

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